

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

MODERN WOMEN'S PROSE OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The article presents women's prose of Kazakhstan in the first quarter of the XXI century using the creative writings of S. Doszhan and Sh. Beisenova as an example. The topics of their works are in a certain way connected with women's fate. The view of the surrounding reality from a female point of view plays the important role. Through the fates of female characters, the authors show the history of the nation and country.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, women's prose, novel, story, tale.

The modern literary landscape of Kazakhstan cannot be imagined without active participation of women – poets and writers. The topics of their works are in a certain way connected with women's fate. The view of the surrounding reality from a female point of view plays the important role.

Member of the Writers' Union of Kazakhstan, Honored Figure of the Republic of Kazakhstan, member of the International Women Writing Guild, writer Saule Doszhan worthily represents women's prose of Kazakhstan in the first quarter of the XXI century. She is known for her novels and stories in which she touches upon the issue of social role of women in modern society.

In 2017, the "Foliant" publishing house published the book "My Alien Heart" [1] by S. Doszhan. The book includes the novels "My Alien Heart", "Devastation", "When a Woman is a Hostage", "Father's Secret Testament" and the stories "White Yurt in the Steppe", "Confession of a Fugitive", "The Curse of Money", "Longing for the Master", "Love of a Hairdresser", "Six Nights Spent with a Beauty". In 2018, the book "My Alien Heart" was translated into German and presented in Berlin as part of the International Forum "Modern Kazakhstani Culture in the Global World".

In the novel "When a Woman is a Hostage" S. Doszhan focuses on family relationships. The author brilliantly reveals the experiences of the main character Asem, who strives to build a career as a public official.

The novel by S. Doszhan "When a Woman is a Hostage" demonstrates the high skill of the writer, which is manifested in several key aspects: stylistic techniques, composition, creation of characters and dialogues. The writer uses a rich and expressive language, which makes the narrative lively and emotionally rich. For example, through figurative expressions and metaphors, she conveys the inner experiences of the characters and the atmosphere of the events described. Frequent use of direct speech helps to more deeply reveal the characters' natures and motives.

Compositionally the novel is structured in such a way that the reader gradually immerses in the world of the characters, learning about their past, personal experiences and current conflicts. The author skillfully alternates narrative passages with dialogues, creating dynamics and holding the reader's attention. There is also

a flashback, which adds depth to the story and allows one to better understand the characters' motivations.

The characters in the novel are depicted very realistically and multifacetedly. S. Doszhan pays attention not only to their appearance and actions, but also to their internal monologues and thoughts, which makes them lively and recognizable. The main character Asem, for example, is shown as a person who values humanity above professionalism, which leads to conflicts with colleagues and authorities. Her desire for justice and kindness is opposed to bureaucratic rigidity and callousness.

"When Asem began her work as head of department, she first met with each employee in private. She wanted to find out their style and methods of work, their marital status, speech culture and ability to present themselves through the interview. Twelve subordinates showed twelve types of character. Each, as far as possible, tried to show their competence" [1, p. 227].

The dialogues in the novel not only reveal the characters' natures, but also advance the plot, deepen the themes and conflicts. They are written naturally and reliably, reflecting the psychological state and social status of the characters. Through the characters' lines, the author conveys not only their thoughts and feelings, but also public moods and the problems of the time.

The theme of the novel touches upon important social and ethical issues, such as humanity in professional activities, the importance of upbringing and education, as well as the role of women in society. These themes are revealed through the prism of personal experiences of the characters, which makes them closer and more understandable to the readers. "After entering the service at the ministry, all family matters unconditionally faded into the background. Both her husband and herself, even her little daughter, before planning anything, always match it with her work schedule. All family matters are postponed until the weekend, when she is free" [1, p. 248].

Prose writer, academician of the Academy of Russian Literature, editor-in-chief of the publishing house "Khudozhestvennaya Literatura" Georgy Pryakhin published a review of the book "Tragedy and Fate" by S. Doszhan, translated into Russian in 2019, in the literary and art magazine "Vtornik" (Moscow, 2022).

G. Pryakhin's response is imbued with empathy and sympathy for the main character of the novel. And

this is natural, since the issue of underground nuclear tests in the city of Semipalatinsk (now the Semey city) in the fifties of the XX century and their consequences will not leave anyone indifferent. S. Doszhan shows these consequences using the example of the fate of one woman who lost her child, and then her husband due to incurable diseases. The peculiarity of the novel is that the narration is in the first person. "The narration is so heartfelt and detailed that at first it seemed to me that everything described in the novel was experienced by the author personally" [2, p. 232]. But G. Pryakhin explains that the book generalizes the fates of many women with whom the writer communicated over several years while preparing this book.

The work of the Kazakhstani writer makes the author of the review think about the fact that recently the theme of nuclear war, namely, its inevitability, is increasingly spreading in the world: "the mankind is beginning to be gradually accustomed to the specter of global death, essentially universal – nuclear" [2, p.233]. In this regard, he notes the relevance of S. Doszhan's book and calls it a feminine protest note.

Highlighting the presence of many precise and figurative observations, signs, dreams, proverbs and sayings in the novel, the Russian writer draws parallels with the Russian folk vocabulary, the dialect. G. Pryakhin is impressed by the theme of hope, which sounds at the end of the novel, the author shows the formation of the character's new destiny, the birth of new love and new life. "The book "Tragedy and Fate" by the Kazakhstani writer S. Doszhan is caused by life. Moreover, it appeals to life. And this is its main merit" [2, p.236] – concludes G. Pryakhin. The translation of the book into Russian was carried out by Gosman Tolegul, the literary editor of the book is Anar Kabdullina.

It should be noted that the book "Tragedy and Fate" was also translated into Japanese. In 2023, presentation of the book was held at the Tokyo National Museum. The initiative to translate the novel came from the Center for the Rapprochement of Cultures under the auspices of UNESCO under the leadership of Olzhas Suleimenov. The translation was carried out by the famous translator Masujima Shigenobu, who speaks Kazakh. In Japan, S. Doszhan was able to visit the city of Hiroshima. In the interview with the Kazakh literary portal, S. Doszhan spoke about the meeting with the Mayor of Hiroshima Kazumi Matsui and the Director of the Hiroshima Memorial Museum Takehiro Kagawa. "Our delegation laid flowers at the memorial to the victims of atomic bombing of Hiroshima. We honored the memory with a minute of silence", recalls S. Doszhan [3].

The topic of nuclear bomb testing in Kazakhstan is continued by the book "When Hope is Alive", published in Almaty in 2021. In it, S. Doszhan tells how the health of the indigenous people of the Semipalatinsk region suffered greatly due to nuclear tests conducted in Kazakhstan during the Soviet era. The book is significant because it is based on real historical facts. From 1949 to 1989, when the last explosion took place, the land and air of the region were subjected to destructive pollution. In 1991, the Semipalatinsk test site was officially closed. The author highlights a tragic page in

the history of Kazakhstan - nuclear tests led to cancer and the birth of disabled children: "Unfortunately, in every family someone suffered from the consequences of nuclear tests" [4, p. 46]. S. Doszhan's trips to this region, where "people overcome tragedy and grief and do not lose hope for a bright future" inspired her to write the book [4, p. 366].

S. Doszhan's mastery is expressed in her ability to create vivid and believable images, use expressive language, and focus on the problems that women face in everyday life. Her works not only captivate the readers, but also make them think about important life issues.

S. Doszhan is a laureate of international and national contests in literature. In 2017, in Stockholm (Sweden), she took third place in the "Open Eurasian Literature Festival and Book Forum-2017". S. Doszhan's books are translated into foreign languages. In 2018, the British publishing house "Hertfordshire Press" published her novella "The Tragedy of a Bastard" in English, which participated in the competition for the International Booker Prize (London). Positive reviews of this work were provided by John Fardon, the writer, laureate of prestigious British awards, and Caroline Walton, the literary critic, member of the British Translators Association.

S. Doszhan was awarded the International Literary Prize "Alash". In 2023, she was awarded the Parasat Order for making a great personal contribution to the development and enhancement of the spiritual and intellectual potential of the Republic.

Sh. Beisenova is a bright representative of modern Kazakh women's prose. In the series "Library of Kazakh Literature" under the program "Publication of Socially Important Types of Literature" of the Ministry of Culture and Information of the Republic of Kazakhstan, a collection of novels and stories by Sh. Beisenova "The Story of One Love" (2011) was published [5]. The works of the writer, Honored figure of Kazakhstan Sh. Beisenova, which are included into the book "The Story of One Love", focus on Kazakh woman. Through the fates of female characters, the author shows the history of the nation and country. Characterizing the creativity of Sh. Beisenova, the critics note "deep knowledge of woman's life, desire to speak out and show the main thing in her fate in close-up" [5, p. 5].

The heroines of the novels "The Last Days of Suzge", "The Story of One Love", "Zagipa" are strong-willed women, with their heroic deeds they can serve as example for many.

The novel "The Last Days of Suzge" by Sh. Beisenova is a historical narrative, in the center of which is the tragic fate of the heroine named Suzge. The action of the story takes place on the background of historical events, when the Kazakh lands were attacked by enemy troops. The novel is written on the basis of a wide range of sources, including archival materials.

The main character, Suzge, is the youngest wife of Kuchum, the ruler of the Siberian Khanate. She lives in the Khan's palace, which was once full of life and laughter, but is now immersed in gloomy silence. "Suzge has long been in deep turmoil, unable to find peace of mind, she feels her soul weakening, undermined by

a dull anxiety. All the same thoughts and feelings, corroding the soul, run and run in a routine circle. The Khan's palace is drowning in gloomy silence. It seemed that the whole world held its breath, listening to what was happening in her soul" [5, p. 11].

Servants and guards begin to avoid her, which increases the feeling of isolation. She reflects on her situation, feeling that her suffering will never end, and there is no escape from the torment of loneliness. The lack of news from her husband increases her anxiety and feeling of loneliness.

At this time, the enemies who captured the capital of the Khanate – the city of Yesker, celebrate their victory, plundering and destroying everything around. Drunkenness and revelry of the enemy troops show how far they are from honor and dignity. Ataman Ermak, realizing that the victory is not yet final, strives for a new battle, which adds tension to what is happening.

Suzge spends her days in thoughts and prayer, her soul is filled with anxiety and anticipation of news. She feels that her palace has become a reflection of her inner state – gloomy and full of heavy expectations.

Suzge is depicted as a woman of extraordinary fortitude and loyalty to her principles. She is not only a symbol of femininity, but also of heroism, reflecting the best features of a Kazakh woman. Secondary characters help to reveal her character, creating contrast and emphasizing her uniqueness. Through interaction with other characters of the novel, Suzge shows her best qualities: wisdom, patience and selflessness.

Possessing inner strength and fortitude, Suzge resists external circumstances. Not wanting to surrender to the enemy, she sacrifices herself. This is how Sh. Beisenova describes this scene: "She stood leaning her back against a tree. Moving her lips, she read a prayer for a long time. The city trembled from the rumble of many hooves. She was no longer afraid of strangers or death itself. She knew that there was one deliverance from the mockery of her body, the abuse of her conscience, slavery and unbearable suffering – this was death" [5, p. 78]. Her story is revealed through the prism of personal experiences and struggle, reflecting the tragedy of a woman's fate.

The novel "The Last Days of Suzge" not only tells about the personal tragedy of the main character, but also reflects the historical and cultural aspects of the life of the Kazakh people. Suzge symbolizes fortitude and courage, her inner world and experiences are a metaphor for suffering and struggle of her people in difficult times. Using the example of the main character, the author shows the importance of fortitude and readiness to withstand any life challenges, emphasizing moral values and cultural heritage of the Kazakh people.

The next novel "The Story of One Love," is based on the memories of the 90-year-old heroine Margua, whose youth was spent in the difficult 1930s. The novel begins with a description of her life before the tragic events. She is a wife, mother and faithful companion of her husband, with whom she has a strong and mutual love. Her husband, a famous literary scholar and public figure, is subjected to Stalin's repressions and is sent into exile in Siberia.

Margua decides to accompany her husband in exile, despite all the difficulties and dangers. The story describes in detail her experiences, daily struggle for survival in harsh conditions of Siberian exile. Despite difficult conditions, she finds strength to support her husband and take care of the children who remained in their homeland.

Margua and her husband live in Siberian exile for many years. Life in exile is full of hardships and suffering, but their love and support help them overcome all challenges. Their relationship serves as an example of deep connection and mutual respect. Margua becomes a symbol of loyalty and devotion, her image personifies the strength of woman's character and ability to selfless love. She not only supports her husband morally, but also actively participates in social life of the exile, helping other repressed people. The secondary characters of the story also play important role, creating the background and emphasizing the main features of Margua.

After many years in exile, thanks to Margua's efforts and unbroken faith, her husband manages to return to his homeland. The author describes their return and difficulties of adapting to a new life. Despite all the suffering they have endured, Margua and her husband find strength for a new beginning. The story is based on real events, which provides the narrative with special strength and persuasiveness.

"The Story of One Love" not only tells the story of one family, but also reflects important historical and social aspects of the life of the Kazakh people during Stalin's repressions. The author emphasizes the value of love, loyalty and moral fortitude. Margua's story teaches the reader that true love and devotion can overcome any obstacles, and the strength of human spirit can endure the most difficult challenges.

The novel "The Story of One Love" is a deeply touching and emotional work that leaves a lasting impression and reminds us of the importance of family values and moral principles. The writer's talent is demonstrated in constructing such an interesting plot that the story is read to the end in one breath.

The novel "Zagipa" tells the story of a woman who faces difficulties and challenges on her life's path. Zagipa, like other heroines of Beysenova, is a symbol of fortitude and inner strength. The plot of the novel is built around her struggle for happiness and well-being of her family, reflecting personal and social conflicts. She takes care of her father-in-law, who needs constant attention because of his health. Her husband, Bolat, does not help her and often causes additional problems because of his drunkenness. Despite this, Zagipa tries to keep the house in order and provides comfort and care to all members of her family.

Zagipa is depicted as a woman with deep inner world and complex experiences. Her psychological portrait is revealed through relationships with others and her personal reflections. The author focuses on her desire to maintain dignity and self-respect in any circumstances. The story reaches its climax when Zagipa decides that she can no longer tolerate such a life. She thinks about changing her fate, although she understands that it will be very difficult to do so.

Sh. Beisenova touches on the topic of women's fate in the context of social inequality and injustice. Through her story, the author raises important issues of social justice and equality, showing how personal fortitude and courage can change fate.

These three stories by Sh. Beisenova are united by common themes of love, loyalty and struggle for justice, reflecting the richness of Kazakh culture and history.

The stories "Indian Summer", "The Night Secret of Rain", "The Bitter Taste of Love", "Sisters" etc. are based on the theme of city life. In them, the writer reflects life as it is. Sh. Beisenova's stories emphasize important aspects of human relationships, such as love, family, and inner strength, helping the reader to understand and appreciate these values more deeply.

The main character of the story "Indian Summer" Akzhamal is a grandmother who takes care of her granddaughter. The action takes place in early autumn, during the Indian summer. Akzhamal reflects on her life and remembers the past. She walks with her granddaughter in the garden, enjoying warm days and beautiful nature. Through interaction with her granddaughter and nature, she feels the restoration of her strength and inner peace. At the end of the story, she realizes that there is deep connection between human and nature that helps to overcome difficulties and find comfort.

The story "The Night Secret of Rain" focuses on the night scene, when the main character listens to the sound of rain and immerses herself in memories and reflections. Rain becomes a symbol of purification and rebirth. Night and rain create atmosphere of mystery in which the character experiences her personal dramas and finds answers to important questions in her life. As a result of these reflections, she comes to new conclusions and decisions that help her cope with difficulties and find inner peace.

The story "The Bitter Taste of Love" tells about complicated love relationships between the characters

who go through many challenges. Love is shown as strong, but sometimes bitter feeling that can bring suffering. The main character faces betrayal and disappointment, but despite this, she continues to believe in love. Through bitterness and pain, she finds the strength to forgive and accept, realizing that love, despite its difficulties, remains important part of life.

The story "Sisters" tells about two sisters who, despite life challenges, maintain their connection and support for each other. The sisters go through many difficulties, including personal dramas and family conflicts, but their mutual understanding helps them overcome all obstacles. At the end of the story, the sisters find comfort and joy in their unity, despite all difficulties they have experienced.

The creativity of Sh. Beisenova is distinguished by deep elaboration of psychological portraits of female characters; one of the features of her creativity is the ability to accurately notice all details of everyday life.

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